

THE POWER OF EFFECTIVE LEADERSHIP: HOW MANAGING TEAMS
TRANSFORMS GOALS INTO RESULTS

Ashurbayev Omar (senior lecturer of Millat Umidi University)

Xusnuddinova Sofiya (student of Millat Umidi University) **ORCID: 0009-0004-3621-1093** sofiyaxusnuddinova@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Leadership plays a crucial role for organization to achieve its goals and objectives. So, this article demonstrates the effect of leadership to team's efficiency, motivation and team members performance. You can see in the real company examples, how the right chosen leadership style can transform goals into results. Then we discussed why leadership style is important to achieve objectives and which one I consider better according to may research. In the end, you can find my own recommendations to develop leadership style in the organization, and some models to use for getting better results in team works.

Key words Leadership style, organization goal, team work, Belbin's team roles, Tuckman model, performance, motivation.

Аннотация

Лидерство играет решающую роль для организации в достижении ее целей и задач. Итак, эта статья демонстрирует влияние лидерства на эффективность команды, мотивацию и производительность членов команды. Вы можете увидеть на реальных примерах компаний, как правильно выбранный стиль лидерства может трансформировать цели в результаты. Затем мы обсудили, почему стиль лидерства важен для достижения целей и какой из них я считаю лучшим по результатам моих исследований. В конце вы найдете мои собственные рекомендации по развитию стиля лидерства в организации, а также некоторые модели, которые можно использовать для достижения лучших результатов в командной работе.

Ключевые слова Стиль лидерства, цель организации, командная работа, командные роли Белбина, модель Такмана, результативность, мотивация.

Annotatsiya

Liderlik tashkilotning maqsad va vazifalariga erishishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Shunday qilib, ushbu maqola liderlikning jamoa samaradorligiga, motivatsiyasiga va jamoa a'zolarining ishlashiga o'z ta'sirini ko'rsatadi. Haqiqiy kompaniya misollarida to'g'ri tanlangan liderlik uslubi maqsadlarni natijalarga qanday aylantirishi mumkinligini ko'rsatadi. Keyin biz nima uchun liderlik uslubi maqsadlarga erishish uchun muhimligini va tadqiqotga ko'ra qaysi biri yaxshiroq deb hisoblaganimni muhokama qildik. Maqolaning ohirgi qismida, siz organizatsiyada liderlik uslubini rivojlantirish bo'yicha o'z tavsiyalarimni va jamoaviy ishlarda yaxshi natijalarga erishish uchun foydalanish uchun ba'zi modellarni topishingiz mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar Liderlik uslubi, organizatsiya maqsadi, jamoaviy ish, Belbinning jamoa rollari, Tuckman modeli, ijro samaradorligi, motivatsiya.

Literature review

➤ Demirtas, O. and Karaca, M. (2020). *Handbook of Leadership Styles*. S.L.: Cambridge Scholars Publis.

This book discusses about dynamic character of leadership styles in the work, with particular attention paid to the significance of position power and authority in the eyes of followers. It emphasizes how economic, behavioral, and mental shifts crucial to make new strategies. The book discusses a number of leadership models, illustrating how dynamic leadership is. It blends classical and modern approaches to provide scholars and practitioners with a thorough reference.

➤ According to this website - West Chester University (2022). *Tuckman's stages of group development*. [online] West Chester University. Available at: <https://www.wcupa.edu/coral/tuckmanStagesGroupDevelopment.aspx>.

CORAL places more emphasis on identifying and supporting teams in their developmental stages than Tuckman's initial method, which concentrated on group evolution. Teams may evolve, progressing to several Tuckman phases like Norming or Performing. Project guides facilitate seamless transitions and teamwork by assisting teams in getting back to perform.

➤ Moultrie, J. (2016). *Belbin's Team Roles*. [online] University of Cambridge. Available at: <https://www.ifm.eng.cam.ac.uk/research/dmg/tools-and-techniques/belbins-team-roles/>.

This website discusses about team roles concept developed by Meredith Belbin in 1981, assists teams in identifying their strengths and limitations so they can work better. It's a popular technique for team development that acknowledges the variety of character types in the most successful teams, despite complaints for being overly simplistic and pigeon-holing.

➤ McPheat, S. (2023). *Elon Musk Leadership Style Explained | MTD Training*. [online] Leadership and Management Training Courses UK | MTD Training. Available at: <https://www.mtdtraining.com/blog/elon-musk-leadership-explained.htm>.

This site demonstrates how transformational leadership style helped Elon Musk to establish companies with great innovation. He is a leader who motivates to innovate new innovations with long term success and new solutions to problems. So his workers should be creative and hard working to achieve career goals.

➤ and, E. (2014). *Financier Worldwide*. [online] Financier Worldwide. Available at: <https://www.financierworldwide.com/efficiency-and-effectiveness-building-a-high-performing-team> [Accessed 26 Dec. 2024].

Workers' commitment, expertise, and specific skills are what propel a company to success. In intricate economic environments, successful teams are essential to conquering obstacles. 53% of respondents said that their performance has greatly improved since switching to a team- or network-based organizational model, demonstrating the tremendous improvement that team-based organizational models bring.

Methods of research:

This paper reviews the literature on leadership style using a secondary-methods approach, examining information from books, published articles, reliable websites government sources, and business outcomes. It also looks at how well models to improve leadership work and how they are applied in businesses. I didn't use primary research method as my research didn't require interviews or surveys to conduct the research.

Data collection

While qualitative research expresses in words, aims to understand concepts, thoughts, or experiences, common methods like: interviews, observations, and literature reviews. Quantitative research, which uses numbers and graphs to test theories and assumptions, establishes generalizable facts about a topic; common methods include observations, and surveys, statistics and analysis. I use both qualitative and quantitative method to research logical facts, to examine influence of leadership on team dynamics and goal achievement. (Streefkerk, 2019)

Analysis

Leadership styles

In the organization its crucial to know your leadership style, so you can determine how effective it works, is your employees satisfied which skills you need to improve to increase your team efficiency and success. There are 6 most common used leadership styles which helps you to achieve organization goals. Companies can use 1 of them mostly but they can use other styles also when they need it according to their task.

(LinkedIn , 2024)

1. Transformational leadership style

Focus of transformational leadership is on adjustments and transformation, motivating followers to go after their expectations from their leader. Focusing on the future, embracing change with ease, and putting people first are all essential traits of transformational leadership. Inspiring their employees to accomplish the organization's objectives, transformational leaders make sure they are able to adjust to and feel at ease with change. Additionally, they acknowledge each person's potential and strive to help them maximize it by enhancing their unique skills and qualities. When a business is looking to make major changes or transformations, this approach

may be quite successful. Leaders who use transformational leadership style motivates its employees to work creatively to innovate new solutions to the issues or new products according to market demand. (IMD, 2022)

2. Transactional style

This leadership style that prioritizes structure, rewarding systems, and penalties, it also called as managerial leadership. Leaders using this leadership style establishes precise team objectives and specifies how teams will be compensated, frequently in the form of cash. Instead of radical organizational changes, this "input and output" approach emphasizes effective routines and processes. When workers would be punished because they couldn't do their task on time or not well others also will be warned to not repeat his or her mistake. But if leader only punishes it can decrease motivation of the team so in transactional style, they also need to reward staffs who worked efficiently and helped to the objectives of organization which inspires others to work better to get reward. (IMD, 2022)

3. Democratic style

A leader that practices democratic leadership bases choices on team participation and is consultative and cooperative. It gives opportunity to workers to say their opinions and ideas, so they can vote for decisions. This style improves high levels of job happiness and productivity, which promotes innovation and involvement. It may be expensive and time-consuming to get team members to agree, though, particularly when decisions must be made fast. (Corporate Finance Institute, 2022)

4. Laissez-Faire Style

In a laissez-faire leadership style, team members are given the resources, knowledge, and tools they need to do their duties. In this style leaders use let them be method so team members may work independently on problem-solving, planning, creating, and decision-making. Creative, talented, and self-motivated workers are empowered by this empowering strategy, which increases productivity and job happiness. Laissez-faire leadership has been found to be the least successful and least fulfilling. (Corporate Finance Institute, 2022)

5. Servant style of leadership

A leader that practices servant leadership puts the needs of their team above their own. High honesty and a healthy company culture are traits of this leadership style that boost team harmony. However, servant leaders can give way to ambitious leaders, it is criticized for its incapacity to react to competitive conditions and don't ending tasks till deadlines. So, servant leadership is a type of leadership by example, where leaders must cultivate, uplift, and motivate their subordinates to get the greatest outcomes. (Corporate Finance Institute, 2022)

6. Bureaucratic style of leadership

There is minimal leeway for flexibility under bureaucratic leadership, which is characterized by a tight adherence to rules and procedures. When employee input deviates from the organization's policies, the leader firmly enforces these regulations. There is a hierarchical authority system with power moving from top to bottom, and new ideas frequently come slowly. Bureaucratic leadership is not appropriate for new, ambitious enterprises because it lacks the drive for creativity or additional effort, even if it has less control and greater flexibility than autocratic

leadership. But it works well for regular workers and is appropriate for positions requiring safety hazards. In general, young, aspirational people are not suited for bureaucratic leadership. (IMD, 2022)

The leadership style chosen by Elon Musk

Now, we can see how *transformational style* of leadership is successfully implemented by businessman and co-founder of companies like Tesla, SpaceX, PayPal -Elon Musk. You can see how this style of leadership can help to achieve business organizations goals and objectives.

A combination of ambition, and receptivity to new ideas and strategies characterize Elon Musk's revolutionary leadership style. He listens to team members' ideas and sets high standards for himself and his businesses, demanding a lot of work and resources. Musk's dedication to creating high-quality goods and his work ethic demonstrate his enthusiasm for quality. His inventive approach, drive for excellence, talent investment, problem-solving abilities, communication skills, flexibility, and staff empowerment are some of his leadership traits. As a result of visionary leadership's encouragement of creativity and risk-taking, ground-breaking goods like SpaceX's reusable rockets and Tesla's Model S electric automobile have successfully launched. Musk's creative method encourages team members to think creatively and express their ideas without worrying about backlash by using technology to discover fresh answers to current issues. (McPheat, 2023)

Also, Elon Musk is renowned for his dedication to moral principles, and ethical standards. He is renowned for taking a forceful approach to successful innovation, emphasizing staff training and fostering a competitive atmosphere. Musk's company culture is centered on having great dreams and pushing people to think creatively and ambitiously. Companies can adapt and maintain their lead in a cutthroat market thanks to this culture of continuous improvement, which acknowledges that greatness is an ongoing process of progress. (Ceoinsight, 2024)

Effect of leadership style

Using transformational leadership style helped Elon Musk to be open to innovation and the growth of ventures. His new innovative ideas like Cybertruck and Model S increased capitalization of Tesla to **\$1,45 trillion**. Tesla employs over 152 000 workers, its crucial to manage, control and give a right direction for employees. To increase sales, value of company (Nasdaq, 2024)

Elon Musk's SpaceX company value increased drastically to \$350 billion based on a secondary share sale, CNBC confirmed in 2024.

Discussion

The role of leadership

Employee happiness, customer loyalty, market reputation, and sustainable development are all components of an organization's success. A company's culture, vision, and mission are all shaped by its leadership, which also affects employee behavior and how adaptable the business is to change. The culture of a firm is its personality, and leaders shape and uphold it. Strong, upbeat cultures boost productivity, reduce attrition, and promote employee engagement. By supporting staff development, giving constructive criticism, and recognizing accomplishments, effective leaders create a healthy work atmosphere. In addition, leaders establish the organization's strategic direction by establishing specific goals and devising plans to reach them. This precise guidance directs choices and synchronizes endeavors with the organization's objectives. Proficient leaders effectively handle change by welcoming it as a chance for development and encouraging a feeling

of community among staff members. To sum up, leadership is about motivating people to reach their full potential, leading by example, encouraging teamwork, and creating an atmosphere that supports creativity rather than about exercising power. (Wilkinson, 2023)

Importance of emotional intelligence for leaders

The capacity to identify, comprehend, and manage one's own emotions as well as those of others is known as emotional intelligence (EI). For leaders to succeed in their positions, it is essential. Self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills are the five main components of emotional intelligence. Leaders that possess emotional intelligence remain humble, regulate their emotions, and uphold high standards for their job. They create safe spaces where workers can express their thoughts, take measured risks, and leverage their feelings to propel the company forward. Leaders with emotional intelligence can plan and prepare for changes without thinking about how it would affect their ego. They also don't hold personal grudges. On the other hand, leaders with low EI have a tendency to lose their cool under pressure, which can result in verbal abuse and passive aggressiveness that undermines team cohesiveness and productivity. (Wilkinson, 2023)

Importance of working in a team to achieve goals of organization and team

The division of challenging duties, the simplification of complicated projects, and the promotion of varied skill sets are all advantages of teamwork in the workplace. It takes active listening, suggestions, dependability, cooperation, flexibility, and dedication to show collaborative abilities. A good team has a balance of duties, complementary abilities, and a strong feeling of unity. In the corporate world, teamwork is crucial because it enhances problem-solving skills, productivity, efficiency, creativity, employee morale, and job satisfaction. It creates a friendly work atmosphere for staff members, encourages candid communication, and values contributions. And in the team work it's important to determine roles of team members, in 1 team its difficult to be 2 leaders as other members don't know whom to follow. It's important to appoint team members roles according to their skills, abilities and personality. (Asana, 2022)

So now I chose Blebin's model to use for appoint team members roles. And it's crucial that in 1 team, there shouldn't be 2 people with same result or roles.

Reccomandation

Belbin's model

A method for building harmonious teams that can work together productively and without conflict is the Belbin team role's structure. In order to maximize each team member's potential and create high-performing teams, it specifies nine different roles or behaviors that are necessary for effective teamwork. Resource Investigator, Teamworker and Co-ordinator, Plant, Monitor Evaluator and Specialist, and Shaper, Implementer and Completer Finisher

Belbin's model promotes strategic decision-making and creative solutions through various roles. Plant solves problems creatively, while Specialists provide in-depth knowledge and abilities, while Monitor Evaluators offer rational advice. Action-oriented roles improve team performance and project outcomes through efficient task execution and obstacle management. Implementation is systematic and reliable, while Shaper propels projects forward. Completer Finisher adheres to strict quality control standards. People-oriented roles improve collaboration, team development, and team culture. Coordinators make wise choices, assign work to best candidates, and maintain focus on goals. Resource investigators are interested, tactful, and cooperative, while team workers are helpful and cooperative. Recognizing and accommodating different work styles can make collaborative project management more feasible. (literature et al., 2023)

Tuckman model

Forming, Storming, Norming, Performing, and Adjourning are the phases of group growth according to Tuckman. These phases support the growth of teams' connections, leadership philosophies, and maturity. The model places a strong emphasis on identifying a team's developmental stage and helping it move into a stage that is compatible with teamwork. Teams frequently emerge and change in the real world as they progress through various stages, such as storming or norming. Project guidelines are essential for assisting teams in progressing to the next phase. Forming includes establishing the team's structure, preventing disagreement, and concentrating on the needs of the group. Storming is focused on human relationships, producing interpersonal disputes, and managing activities and processes. In order for shared leadership to become effective, norming entails developing new ways of doing and being together. For shared leadership to be successful, team members must learn to trust one another. Data flow, group member participation, and innovation are all part of stage three. Fear of a potential split may result from the norming period. True interdependence, adaptability, and comprehension of team requirements are all part of stage four. This stage necessitates joint leadership and is very productive. When team members are prepared to go, adjourning takes place, which causes a great deal of disturbance. (West Chester University, 2022)

Conclusion

For a company to succeed, leadership is essential because it fosters teamwork, creativity, and alignment. Performance may be improved by comprehending leadership styles and customizing efficient strategies or models like Tuckman and Belbin. It is crucial to embrace flexibility, emotional intelligence, and strategic vision.

REFERENCE LIST

and, E. (2014). *Financier Worldwide*. [online] Financier Worldwide. Available at: <https://www.financierworldwide.com/efficiency-and-effectiveness-building-a-high-performing-team> [Accessed 26 Dec. 2024].

Asana (2022). *Teamwork in the Workplace: 11 Benefits (With Examples) [2023]* • Asana. [online] Asana. Available at: <https://asana.com/ru/resources/teamwork-in-the-workplace>.

Ceoinsight (2024). *Elon Musk and Transformational Leadership*. [online] www.ceoinsightsasia.com. Available at: <https://www.ceoinsightsasia.com/business-inside/elon->

musk-and-transformational-leadership--nwid-12277.html.

Corporate Finance Institute (2022). *Leadership Styles*. [online] Corporate Finance Institute. Available at: <https://corporatefinanceinstitute.com/resources/management/leadership-styles/>.

Demirtas, O. and Karaca, M. (2020). *Handbook of Leadership Styles*. S.L.: Cambridge Scholars Publis.

IMD (2022). *The 6 Most Common Leadership Styles & How to Find Yours*. [online] www.imd.org. Available at: <https://www.imd.org/blog/leadership/leadership-styles/>.

LinkedIn (2024). *Leadership Styles*. [online] Licdn.com. Available at: https://media.licdn.com/dms/image/D4D12AQEq0Y1P0m4zJA/article-cover_image-shrink_600_2000/0/1687765173994?e=2147483647&v=beta&t=WcVUIVOGgdxr5ylkfkAZzYqw9qkbJIEBSUdlrhDvAo [Accessed 26 Dec. 2024].

literature, G.W. is a content creator within the marketing team at B.S. loves creating actionable content in different formats to help others achieve more project success G. spent far too long at university studying E., Learning, W.I. a L.-L.L. of, time, upskilling I. her free, Gym, S.E. a C.S. at the, Book, T. into a G. and dog, walking the beautiful G. coastline with her (2023). *How to Use Belbin Team Roles for Your Projects*. [online] BrightWork.com. Available at: <https://www.brightwork.com/blog/belbin-team-roles-projects>.

McPheat, S. (2023). *Elon Musk Leadership Style Explained | MTD Training*. [online] Leadership and Management Training Courses UK | MTD Training. Available at: <https://www.mtdtraining.com/blog/elon-musk-leadership-explained.htm>.

Moultrie, J. (2016). *Belbin's Team Roles*. [online] University of Cambridge. Available at: <https://www.ifm.eng.cam.ac.uk/research/dmg/tools-and-techniques/belbins-team-roles/>.

Nasdaq (2024). *Tesla Inc (TSLA) Stock Price & News - Google Finance*. [online] Google Finance. Available at: <https://www.google.com/finance/quote/TSLA:NASDAQ?sa=X&sqi=2&ved=2ahUKEwiovoq-78SKAxWEJRAIHRT0MyUQ3ecFegQIQxAg> [Accessed 26 Dec. 2024].

Streefkerk, R. (2019). *Qualitative vs. quantitative research | differences, examples & methods*. [online] Scribbr. Available at: <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/qualitative-quantitative-research/>.

West Chester University (2022). *Tuckman's stages of group development*. [online] West Chester University. Available at: <https://www.wcupa.edu/coral/tuckmanStagesGroupDelvelopment.aspx>.

Wilkinson, M. (2023). *The Role of Leadership in Organizational Success*. [online] Leadership Strategies. Available at: <https://www.leadstrat.com/the-role-of-leadership-in-organizational-success/>.